

The MARVEL Data Corpus: A Secure and Privacy-Aware Multimodal Big Data Repository for Smart Cities Research

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Abstract— Smart cities increasingly rely on Big Data, IoT, cloud computing, and AI to enhance urban services. However, limited access to public datasets hampers research and innovation. This paper presents the MARVEL Data Corpus, a large-scale, multimodal repository developed under the EU-funded MARVEL project. It includes 1.1PB of anonymized audio-visual data from Malta, Gozo, Trento, and Novi Sad, captured via surveillance systems and drones. The repository features 52,000 snippet files across 64 datasets, with 35 publicly available under a Creative Commons license. Use cases cover traffic monitoring, emergency response, public safety, and event analysis. Data is anonymized at the edge to ensure privacy compliance. The infrastructure is built on Hadoop and HBase, with access via APIs and a web-based Angular GUI. An Augmentation Engine enables data transformations to support AI model training. The MARVEL Data Corpus addresses the lack of open, privacy-aware smart city datasets, promoting AI research and data-driven innovation.

Keywords— smart cities, open datasets, multi-modal data sources, security, safety, smart city monitoring, urban planning, Big Data, Hadoop, HBase

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart cities have emerged as complex, data-driven ecosystems supported by widespread deployment of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, such as cameras, microphones, and sensors [1]. These systems generate vast volumes of data that reflect urban dynamics and citizen activities. However, the high-throughput, real-time nature of this data presents challenges for effective processing, analytics, and decision-making [2]. Traditional methods often fall short in extracting actionable insights at scale, highlighting the need for modern approaches capable of extreme-scale data analytics [2].

Despite their potential [3], smart cities face a critical limitation: the lack of publicly available, high-quality datasets [4]. This gap hinders progress in both academic research and industrial innovation, limiting the development of AI-driven solutions for urban safety, planning, and sustainability.

To address these issues, the EU-funded MARVEL project developed a platform for collecting and processing

multimodal data from smart city infrastructures – primarily surveillance systems – while ensuring privacy, security, and compliance with data protection regulations. A key outcome is the MARVEL Data Corpus, a large-scale, open-access repository [5] designed to: i) support research in audio-visual analytics, ii) structure and analyze real-world experimental data, and iii) foster the European data economy through responsible data sharing.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; Section 3 presents the architecture of the MARVEL Data Corpus; Section 4 describes the Augmentation Engine; Section 5 outlines the use cases and datasets; and Section 6 concludes with future directions.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Smart cities and Application

Smart cities employ digital technologies to enhance the performance and well-being of urban areas [6]. These technologies help cities manage everything from traffic and waste to energy and infrastructure. The concept integrates Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and various physical devices connected to the IoT network to optimize the efficiency of city operations and services. For example, surveillance cameras and IoT sensors are ubiquitous in smart cities, providing critical data that helps manage traffic flow, monitor environmental conditions, and enhance public safety. Machine learning (ML) plays a significant role in processing this data, enabling systems to predict patterns and improve decision-making without human intervention. Among others, ML applications in smart cities include predictive maintenance and replanning of urban infrastructure, optimization of traffic routing, and personalized public services, enhancing both efficiency and sustainability [6].

B. Technical, Security, and Privacy Challenges

Smart cities face significant technical challenges related to scalability, interoperability, and real-time data processing demands [7]. As urban environments become increasingly

digitized, they also become targets for cyber-attacks, raising substantial security and privacy concerns. Ensuring the security of IoT devices and the data they generate involves safeguarding against threats that could disrupt city operations or compromise sensitive information. Privacy is another critical concern, as the collection and analysis of vast amounts of data about individuals' activities can lead to breaches of privacy if not managed with robust protocols. Effective encryption and anonymization, regular security updates, and strict data governance policies are essential to address these challenges and protect against data theft and other malicious activities. Privacy concerns are not only concentrated on criminals, but on governments and/or other authorities that could misuse those pieces of information and violate a person's rights.

C. System Architectures

The complexity of smart city settings requires modern system architectures. Edge to Fog to Cloud (E2F2C) computing [8]-[9] offer layered solutions to handle the massive data flows in smart cities, supporting low-latency, scalability, and efficient data processing. Edge computing processes data at or near the source of data generation, significantly reducing latency by not transmitting vast amounts of data to distant cloud servers, and enhancing security and privacy properties (i.e., voice/face anonymization of surveillance systems at the smart camera end). Fog computing extends the cloud closer to the data sources, offering a decentralized computing infrastructure that ensures shorter response times and improved connectivity. In combination, these architectures can process and analyze data locally in real-time, enhancing the efficiency and responsiveness of smart city applications. They are particularly effective in scenarios requiring immediate analytical insights, such as traffic management systems or emergency response services. Moreover, integrating these architectures can provide a more robust framework for data privacy and security, distributing storage and processing tasks across a hierarchical network. Cloud aggregates data from the underlying subsystems, performs computational expensive processing and ML, and delivers the smart city applications.

D. Implementation of Big Data Repositories

The implementation of efficient repositories for Big Data and extreme scale analytics is crucial in managing the voluminous and diverse datasets generated by smart city applications [10]-[12]. Hadoop [13] and HBase [14] are two widely used open-source technologies [15]. Hadoop allows for the distributed processing of large data sets across clusters of computers using simple programming models. It is designed to scale up from a single server to thousands of machines, each offering local computation and storage. Similarly, HBase, a non-relational, distributed database running on top of Hadoop, provides real-time read/write access to those large datasets. By leveraging these technologies, smart cities can efficiently process, store, and analyze Big Data to improve urban management and policy decisions, enhancing service delivery and infrastructure management.

E. Availability of Open Data Sets

One of the significant obstacles in the advancement of smart city solutions is the scarcity of publicly available datasets, which restricts research and development in this domain [16]. While there are numerous sources of urban data,

much of it is siloed within private entities or restricted due to privacy concerns. This limitation hinders the potential for innovation and collaborative research. Currently available open datasets primarily cover areas such as public transport networks, energy consumption metrics, and municipal activities, but they often lack the depth or breadth required for advanced AI research and development [16]-[17]. Use-cases covered by these datasets include traffic flow analysis, environmental monitoring, and public resource usage, which are invaluable for testing hypotheses and developing models. However, the need for more comprehensive datasets encompassing diverse urban dynamics is critical to foster broader advancements in smart city technologies. Efforts to expand access to high-quality, anonymized datasets could significantly enhance the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications, driving forward the capabilities of smart cities.

F. The MARVEL Platform

The scarcity of publicly available datasets from smart cities poses a significant challenge for researchers and practitioners in the field of ML. Smart cities generate vast amounts of data through interconnected devices and sensors, providing a rich source for developing and testing ML algorithms. However, due to privacy concerns, security issues, and proprietary considerations, many cities are reluctant to release their datasets to the public. The sensitive nature of the information collected, such as individual mobility patterns or environmental sensor data, requires careful handling to prevent misuse. Striking a balance between the potential for innovation through ML research and the protection of citizens' privacy and security remains a complex task. As a result, the limited availability of comprehensive and diverse smart city datasets hampers the progress of ML research in urban environments, impeding the development of robust and effective algorithms tailored to the intricacies of modern city living.

This work explores modern applications of Big Data in smart cities, focusing on their transformative impact across sectors such as transportation, energy management, and public safety. It critically examines the landscape of existing repositories and identifies the gaps in public data availability. By analyzing case studies from leading smart cities, this paper highlights the disparity between data-rich applications and the scarcity of corresponding datasets that are openly accessible. We propose a framework for enhancing data sharing and transparency, aiming to bolster research and enable equitable advancements in smart city technologies. This study underscores the need for a concerted effort to build comprehensive, publicly accessible Big Data repositories to realize the full potential of smart cities.

Data are gathered from various sources (i.e., surveillance cameras, microphones, and drones), are anonymized, annotated, and augmented throughout the Edge-to-Fog-to-Cloud (E2F2C) architecture of MARVEL [18], and are stored in the form of datasets in the MARVEL Data Corpus repository. Then, the datasets are either disseminated publicly as open datasets or are utilized internally by MARVEL's AI/ML components to enhance their training procedures.

Henceforth, the goals of MARVEL can be outlined as follows: i) develop a privacy-conscious solution to unveil valuable insights aimed at enhancing the quality of life, ii) facilitate decision-making through event detection and situational awareness in smart city environments, iii)

overcome technological silos to foster integrated and collaborative solutions, iv) validate the system in real-world scenarios for practical applicability, and v) contribute significantly to extremely large-scale audio-video datasets, thereby supporting the European data-driven economy.

MARVEL’s vision is to gather, analyze, and perform data mining on multi-modal audio-visual data streams originating from a Smart City, and therefore, provide decision-makers with insights to enhance the quality of life for citizens and improve the services offered to them. All while adhering to ethical standards and privacy constraints in a responsible AI fashion.

III. MARVEL DATA CORPUS

This section presents the implementation of the main MARVEL Data Corpus repository.

A. Repository Overview and Main Technologies

Technically, the MARVEL Data Corpus is a Big Data repository storing datasets collected during the project from Trento, Malta, Novi Sad University, and Gozo [18]. It is deployed on the PSNC cloud infrastructure in Poland, distributed across several Virtual Machines (VMs) with 100–250 TB storage each. The backend combines Hadoop for distributed file storage [13] and HBase for metadata indexing [14], [19]. Users can interact with the system through RESTful APIs and two Angular-based GUIs—one private (internal access) and one public (for open datasets) [20].

Initially, all data are stored privately and anonymized using MARVEL’s VideoAnony [21] and AudioAnony [22] tools. Upon verification, data owners decide whether to release the datasets publicly. Users may also apply data augmentation using libraries such as Keras [23], TensorFlow [24], imgaug [25], audiomentations [26], and torch-audiomentations [27].

Ingested data typically pass through anonymisation at the Fog or Cloud layers, though direct Edge-level ingestion from cameras has also been tested. The SmartViz component can automatically analyze data streams [28]-[29] and generate annotated snippets [30]-[31], which are managed by StreamHandler [32] and distributed via a Kafka message broker [33]-[34]. This enables the generation of event-specific datasets beyond continuous recordings.

The platform underwent two internal and one external usability evaluations, along with dedicated security and privacy assessments. Security audits using the Assurance Platform [35]-[36] and CVE-based vulnerability scans [37] found no critical issues. GDPR compliance was validated through the SENTINEL platform [38]-[39].

All public datasets are licensed under Creative Commons, and the software backend will be released as open-source under Apache 2.0 to encourage reuse and adoption.

1) Hadoop repository

Hadoop [13] is a widely used framework in Big Data applications due to its scalability, fault tolerance, and cost-effective storage through the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS). Its parallel processing capabilities accelerate data tasks, and its flexibility allows handling both structured and unstructured data. The comprehensive ecosystem includes tools for processing, storage, querying, and real-time processing. As an open-source framework with a large community, it encourages innovation and customization. The

optimization of data locality, proven reliability, and successful implementations by major enterprises further solidify Hadoop’s position in managing and processing massive datasets within the dynamic landscape of Big Data technologies.

B. Infrastructure & Deployment

The MARVEL Data Corpus was deployed on PSNC’s cloud infrastructure, designed to scale up to 3.3 PB. Initially provisioned with limited storage, capacity was incrementally expanded as usage exceeded 80%, currently reaching 1.1 PB.

The infrastructure is based on a Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) and HBase NoSQL database [19], a common framework for Big Data repositories. The deployment spans two PSNC regional data centers (DCW and BST), using eight Virtual Machines (VMs). One acts as the Master Node, running core Hadoop/HBase services, while the others serve as Data Nodes. Zookeeper manages HBase, and Ambari handles database queries.

Storage volumes per VM are capped at 250 TB to maintain performance, balancing throughput with resource utilization. Larger disks are possible but degrade read/write efficiency.

SSH key-based authentication secures inter-node communication, and 1Gbps internal links support networking. The Assurance Platform monitors HDFS/HBase availability, deploying ELK Beats to collect operational metrics.

The system is easily scalable—new VMs can be configured and integrated into the cluster by updating the Master Node’s configuration. This modular setup allows for straightforward growth to meet future storage and performance needs.

IV. AUGMENTATION ENGINE

This section presents the implementation details for the Augmentation Engine that is running as an internal service of the main repository in order to produce audio and video augmented versions of the original datasets.

A. Augmentations in ML

An important feature of the MARVEL Data Corpus is the integration of data augmentation techniques, which enhance machine learning (ML) model performance and robustness. In ML, augmenting datasets – by applying transformations such as brightness shifts, rotations, or noise – improves generalization and helps models adapt to varying real-world conditions. For example, a video captured in the morning can be augmented to simulate afternoon lighting, making the trained model more effective across time-of-day variations.

Augmentation serves several purposes: i) increases data diversity, helping models generalize better, ii) improves robustness to transformations like scale, lighting, or orientation, iii) addresses data scarcity by expanding small labeled datasets, iv) acts as regularization, reducing overfitting to specific data features, and v) enhances realism, supporting performance in diverse, real-world scenarios.

In the context of smart cities, where collecting labeled data is challenging, augmentation plays a crucial role in training adaptable AI systems. MARVEL supports this through built-in augmentation pipelines that allow users to generate varied dataset versions tailored to their specific ML tasks.

B. Implementation and Supported Augmenters

To support the training of robust machine learning models, a dedicated Augmentation Engine was deployed within the MARVEL Data Corpus infrastructure. This engine enables the transformation of audio and video datasets by simulating conditions such as different times of day or weather scenarios (e.g., rain filters), using state-of-the-art Python-based augmentation techniques.

Users can apply augmentations via a Command Line Interface (CLI) by specifying input/output directories and selecting desired parameters. The system supports continuous or on-demand augmentation, and leverages open-source libraries like Keras, TensorFlow, imgaug, audiomentations, and torch-audiomentations for scalability and performance. Parallel execution and multi-core support (CPU/GPU) are integrated.

Two predefined augmentation profiles were designed in consultation with ML experts: i) Video augmentations: brightness adjustment, grayscale, noise addition, pixelation, contrast, rotation, flipping, and compression artifacts, and ii) Audio augmentations: pitch scaling, time stretching, noise injection, air absorption, MP3 compression, and resampling.

In the Gozo use case, the full video augmentation pipeline was automated. After anonymisation, video files are stored per stream, processed through the augmentation profile, and stored in structured folders. Each set of augmented files is compressed and prepared for ingestion.

Two ingestion flows are used: one for original files and another for the augmented dataset, ensuring both are properly indexed and accessible for research and training purposes.

V. THE INGESTED DATASETS

This Section presents: i) the use cases, ii) stream sources, and the datasets (original and augmented) that are available in the private and public interfaces of the Corpus.

A. Use Cases

Datasets were generated from 10 piloting use cases across four partners [18]

Municipality of Trento (MT): i) MT1 – Crowded Area Monitoring: Detects unusual crowd behaviors to alert local police and prevent safety risks, ii) MT2 – Criminal Behavior Detection: Identifies theft, aggression, and drug-related incidents, especially at night, iii) MT3 – Parking Surveillance: Monitors vehicle positions, damage, and obstructions in parking areas, and iv) MT4 – Urban Analytics for Planning: Analyzes people and vehicle movements to support long-term public policy.

Green Roads Malta (GRN): i) GRN1 – Vulnerable Road Users: Detects cyclists, pedestrians, and micro-mobility at junctions to alert vehicle drivers, ii) GRN2 – Driver Behavior Monitoring: Tracks speeding and unsafe lane changes to support safety campaigns, iii) GRN3 – Traffic Anomalies: Detects congestion and disruptions to inform drivers or infer nearby issues, and iv) GRN4 – Traffic Trajectories: Collects traffic pattern data to inform infrastructure and mobility planning.

University of Novi Sad (UNS): i) NS1 – Drone Surveillance: Uses drones for crowd monitoring at events in areas with limited infrastructure, and ii) UNS2 – Drone-Based

Emotion Recognition: Employs sensor-equipped drones for detailed event analysis and alarm validation.

Municipality of Gozo (MGOZO): While no standalone use case was defined, Gozo contributed video streams supporting similar goals as GRN1–GRN4, such as urban planning and traffic analysis.

B. Stream Sources and Datasets

In total, 29 distinct stream sources have been exploited. From MT, 17 surveillance cameras have been integrated from the areas Duomo Garibaldi, Duomo Nord, Piazza Fiera, Piazza SMMaggiore, Piazza Dante, Park Zuffo, Zuffo Berlino, Zuffo SS Cos-ma-Damiano, Dogana, and Pozzo. GRN utilized 3 surveillance cameras around the city of Malta. UNS run 2 main use cases with drone recordings. From Gozo 7 public cameras have been provided, producing different datasets for each camera. Video recordings have been captured of the vehicle queuing area at the Gozo Channel ferry terminal, as well as from the marshalling front area, the Mgarr shore street (lower, middle, and upper street views), and the Cirkewwa Marshalling area (front and side views). Augmentations for these datasets were also produced in a semi-automated fashion. In general, the cameras could capture both video and audio data, but in most scenarios, only one of the options was used, based on the use cases' minimum requirements.

Each of the constructed datasets contains snippet files from a single streaming source. Currently, there are around 52,000 snippet files (audio, video, and audio-video) within around 64 datasets, 12 of which are augmented versions of the original ones. From them, 35 datasets and 28,500 snippets from GRN, UNS, and MGOZO are public (the 29 datasets of MT are confidential). The total size of the Corpus is around 1.1PBs.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the MARVEL Data Corpus, a scalable, secure, and privacy-aware Big Data repository designed to support research and innovation in smart cities. Developed within the EU-funded MARVEL project, the Corpus serves as a unique resource that addresses key challenges in the domain – particularly the scarcity of publicly available multimodal datasets, the need for GDPR-compliant data pipelines, and the demand for real-world data to train and validate AI models. The infrastructure, deployed on a cloud environment provided by PSNC, leverages proven Big Data technologies such as Hadoop and HBase, supported by a modular architecture that allows future expansion up to several petabytes. A web-based GUI, RESTful APIs, and open licensing under Creative Commons make the platform both accessible and reusable for external users. Importantly, the integration of real-time anonymization (VideoAnony, AudioAnony), data augmentation, and AI-based event detection pipelines sets the foundation for privacy-preserving, AI-ready urban data analytics. To date, the Corpus has integrated data from 29 streaming sources, resulting in over 52,000 snippet files across 64 datasets, of which 35 are publicly available. This includes diverse use cases such as traffic monitoring, public safety, urban planning, and drone-based event surveillance. Moving forward, the MARVEL Data Corpus will continue to evolve as a reference implementation for trustworthy data sharing in smart cities. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset collection, improving anonymization techniques, enabling real-time AI

inference capabilities, and ensuring long-term sustainability through open-source release and collaboration with new stakeholders. Ultimately, the MARVEL Data Corpus contributes to the vision of data-driven, citizen-centric smart cities, enabling researchers, policymakers, and industry to co-create intelligent urban solutions while upholding the highest standards of privacy, security, and ethical AI.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kirimtat, et al. Future trends and current state of smart city concepts: a survey. *IEEE Access* 2020, 8: 86448-86467.
- [2] E. Gilman, et al. Addressing data challenges to drive the transformation of smart cities. *ACM Transactions on Intelligent Systems and Technology* 2024, 15(5): 1-65.
- [3] P. Battistoni. Data driven smart cities and data spaces. *International Symposium: New Metropolitan Perspectives (NMP)*, Springer, LNNS 639, pp. 378-388, 2023.
- [4] K. D. C. Adje, et al. Smart city based on Open Data: a survey. *IEEE Access* 2023, 11: 56726-56748.
- [5] MARVEL Data Corpus public website, 2023-2025. Available at <https://datacorpus.marvel-project.eu/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [6] T. Singh, et al. A decade review on smart cities: paradigms, challenges and opportunities. *IEEE Access* 2022, 10: 68319-68364.
- [7] J. Wu, et al. Big Data meet green challenges: Big Data toward green applications. *IEEE Systems Journal* 2016, 10(3): 888-900.
- [8] M. Marjani, et al. Big IoT Data analytics: architecture, opportunities, and open research challenges. *IEEE Access* 2017, 5: 5247-5261.
- [9] Y. Sasaki. A survey on IoT Big Data analytic systems: current and future. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 2022, 9(2): 1024-1036.
- [10] F. Alam, et al. Data fusion and IoT for smart ubiquitous environments: a survey. *IEEE Access* 2017, 5: 9533-9554.
- [11] T. P. D. Silva, et al. Fpg computing platforms for smart city applications: a survey. *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology* 2022, 22(4): 1-31.
- [12] M. Sookhak, et al. Security and privacy of smart cities: a survey, research issues and challenges. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* 2019, 21(2): 1718-1743.
- [13] Hadoop, Apache. Available at <https://hadoop.apache.org/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [14] HBase, Apache. Available at <https://hbase.apache.org/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [15] S. Guan, et al. Hadoop-based secure storage solution for big data in cloud computing environment. *Digital Communications and Networks* 2024, Elsevier, KeAi, 10(1): 227-236.
- [16] H. B. Abdalla, et al. Big Data: past, present, and future insights. *Asia Pacific Conference on Computing Technologies, Communications and Networking*, ACM, Chengdu, China, 26-27 June, pp. 60-70, 2024.
- [17] E. M. Quafiq, et al. Data architecture and Big Data analytics in smart cities. *26th International Conference on Knowledge-Based and Intelligent Information & Engineering Systems (KES)*, Elsevier, pp. 4123-4131, 2022.
- [18] D. Bajovic, et al. MARVEL: Multimodal Extreme Scale Data Analytics for Smart Cities Environments. *4th International Balkan Conference on Communications and Networking (BalkanCom)*, Novi Sad, Serbia, pp. 1-5, 2021.
- [19] T. Hussain, A. Sanga, S. Mongia. *Big Data Hadoop Tools and Technologies: A Review*. *International Conference on Advancements in Computing & Management (ICACM)*, SSRN, Jaipur, India, pp. 574-578, 2019.
- [20] Angular 2.0, Google. Available at <https://angular.io/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [21] A. Ancilotto, F. Paissan, E. Farella. XimSwap: Many-to-Many Face Swapping for TinyML. *ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems* 2024, 23(3)49:1-16.
- [22] F. Burkhardt, et al. Masking Speech Contents by Random Splicing: is Emotional Expression Preserved?. *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, Rhodes Island, Greece, pp. 1-5, 2023.
- [23] F. Chollet. Keras: Deep Learning for humans. Available at <https://keras.io/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [24] Google. TensorFlow: An Open Source Machine Learning Framework for Everyone. Available at <https://www.tensorflow.org/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [25] A. Jung. imgaug: image augmentation in machine learning experiments. Available at <https://imgaug.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [26] I. Jordal. audiomentations: a Python library for audio data augmentation. Available at <https://github.com/iver56/audiomentations> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [27] Asteroid-team. torch-audiomentations: Audio data augmentation in PyTorch. Available at <https://github.com/asteroid-team/torch-audiomentations> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [28] A. Bakhtiarnia, Q. Zhang, A. Iosifidis. Accurate Gigapixel Crowd Counting by Iterative Zooming and Refinement. *IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing (ICASSP 2024)*, Seoul, Korea, pp. 1-6, 2024.
- [29] A. Mesaros, et al. Low-complexity acoustic scene classification. Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events Challenge. Available at <https://dcase.community/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [30] A. Bakhtiarnia, Q. Zhang, A. Iosifidis. PromptMix: Textto-image diffusion models enhance the performance of lightweight networks. *International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN 2023)*, Queensland, Australia, pp. 1-8, 2023.
- [31] A. Conti, et al. Cluster-level pseudo-labelling for source-free cross-domain facial expression recognition. *33rd British Machine Vision Conference (BMVC 2022)*, London, UK, pp. 1-13, 2022.
- [32] T.P. Raptis, et al. Engineering Resource-Efficient Data Management for Smart Cities with Apache Kafka. *Future Internet* 2023, MDPI, 15(2): 1-43.
- [33] T.P. Raptis and A. Passarella. A Survey on Networked Data Streaming With Apache Kafka. *IEEE Access* 2023, 11: 85333-85350.
- [34] Kafka Message Broker, Apache. Available at <https://kafka.apache.org/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [35] G. Hatzivasilis, et al. Continuous Security Assurance of Modern Supply-Chain Ecosystems with Application in Autonomous Driving: The FISHY approach for the secure autonomous driving domain. *IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (CSR)*, pp. 464-469, 2023.
- [36] E. Lakka, et al. Incident Handling for Healthcare Organizations and Supply-Chains. *IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications (ISCC)*, pp. 1-7, 2022.
- [37] Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE), MITRE. Available at <https://cve.mitre.org/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [38] SENTINEL Project, Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe, EU GA-101021659, 2021-2024. Available at <https://sentinel-project.eu/> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [39] General Data Protection Regulation 2016. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [40] Innovation Radar <https://innovation-radar.ec.europa.eu> (Accessed 20th April 2025).
- [41] A. Buslaev, et al. Alumentations: Fast and Flexible Image Augmentations. *Information* 2020, MDPI, 11(2): 1-20.
- [42] L. Zanella, et al. Responsible AI at the edge: towards privacy-preserving smart cities. *Ital-IA 2022 Convegno del Laboratorio nazionale CINI-AIIS*, Torino, Italy, 9-11 February 2022.
- [43] Ultralytics YOLOv5 for object detection, instance segmentation and image classification, PyTorch. Available at https://pytorch.org/hub/ultralytics_yolov5/ (Accessed 20th April 2025).